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Run Browser > DRR395672

YK686 (DRR395672)

- Metadata
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Run

Run	Spots	Bases	Size	GC Content	Data Status	Published
DRR395672	68.3k	18.4M	6.2MB	48.8%	Public	2024-04-08

Quality graph [\(smaller\)](#)

[Legend](#)

Experiment

Experiment	Library Name	Platform	Strategy	Source	Selection	Layout	Action
DRX381451		Illumina	AMPLICON	GENOMIC	PCR	PAIRED	BLAST

Biosample

Biosample	Sample Description	Organism
SAMD00515458 (DRS373763)		Pseudocolus schellenbergiae

Bioproject

Bioproject	SRA Study	Title
PRJDB13910	DRP011432	Coevolution of ectomycorrhizal fungi and angiosperm at the late Cretaceous drives host-fungus co-diversification

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